

Exploring YouTube Application in a Language Learning Environment for Quality Learning Access in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines Exploring YouTube Application in a Language Learning Environment for Quality Learning access in Nigeria. It explains the concept of YouTube application and other ICT tools in English as Second Language classrooms and explains quality criteria for using YouTube application as an educational tool. This paper reviews literature and gives a scholarly background to the study by reviewing some contributions made by various researchers and institutions on YouTube, students' motivation and learning styles, particularly the types of videos in YouTube and language learning resources on YouTube application. The paper discusses the limitations of YouTube application and benefits of its adoption and implementation and discusses YouTube application and video sharing. The major conclusion of the study is that using YouTube application videos as one and readily available source of authentic material will encourage the students to interact actively in class and further develop their language skills as they are eager to gain deeper understanding of the subject matter. The paper then recommends that YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom by teachers for various teaching such as vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not.

Keywords: YouTube, Internet, Information and Communication Technology, video and Google

Introduction

The arrival of digital technologies such as the internet has resulted in a new generation of individually literate called the Net Generation (Nguyen & Tri, 2014). Due to the emergence of this technical literacy people, their learning style is differing from the previous generations. Thus, this led to an integrated approach and a paradigm shift in teaching which have witnessed an adoption of a new method of teaching using YouTube videos in the classroom. This approach has brought new insights to pedagogy in higher institution and it is believed that the use of YouTube as a teaching tool could have an effect on the level of student engagement. The use of YouTube and other Web 2.0 technologies in education has been proposed as a tool to engage new generation students (Duffy, 2018; Roodt & Peier, 2013).

In February of 2005, Steve Chen, Chad Hurley, and Jawed Karim founded YouTube with the domain name <http://www.YouTube.com>. The site was created as a forum for people to create and share short video clips online. Soon, the website has gained the popularity and many people subscribe to it. The popularity of the website has drawn the attention of Google Company leaders. They have realized the potential role that YouTube will play in the people's life in terms of education, health, politics and economy. So, the company acquired the website in 2006. In the current design of the YouTube website, there are several categories where people can find what they are interested in such as education, music, news and sports. YouTube is a very attractive social medium that contributes to the global education (Duffy, 2018). It is being increasingly used by educators to teach the English language (Terantino, 2011). It "offers fast and fun access to language and culture-based videos and instruction from all over the globe" (Terantino, 2011, p. 11). In other words, YouTube is making new demands on learning that are changing the learning ecology (Chhabra, 2012). Every year, YouTube official website <http://www.YouTube.com> shares astonishing statistics about the use of the YouTube worldwide.

According to the press link "<http://www.YouTube.com/t/press-statistics>", YouTube is localized in 43 countries and across 60 languages; YouTube had more than 1 trillion views or around 140 views for every person on the Earth. 100 million people take a social action on YouTube (likes, shares, comments, etcetera) every week. These statistics show the influence of YouTube on sharing information and knowledge with other people. Due to the popularity of the website, its free-of-charge availability and easiness of use, many language teachers have started to use the website to teach different languages by uploading language learning videos. Language learners around the world like these videos, and some of these videos have reached millions of views. For example, the video titled. "Learning English–Lesson One (Introduction)" has more than 8 million views so far. YouTube has become an important tool in many universities and colleges around the world. According to Web Analytics Association (2006), MySpace, Facebook and YouTube are the top three favorable websites for university students. Therefore, the emergence of digital technologies such as internet and the worldwide web has made the use of YouTube in

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classroom a possibility. Today, the new technology has provided a lot of opportunities to enhance the quality of teaching and learning such as the use of internet and YouTube videos. Many Nigerian university students use these technologies to help them do their assignments and other language learning tasks (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). This technology also helped them to learn the English language as well as enhance their proficiency level. YouTube is featured as something very authentic and able to help the students because it has been reported that the lack of English language proficiency has often been mentioned as one of the major factors contributing to graduate unemployment (Duffy, 2018). How students learn and gain information from YouTube in learning the English language is very important because it will help the educators to identify the students' preference, interest and types of material that they use to enhance learning. Therefore, by using a variety of instructional methods and learning activities in the classroom or via online education can help enrich the learning environment of the students (Rinji & Akintunde, 2019).

Since the use of YouTube videos to learn English language is still a new idea, how it can be used in facilitating language learning in class effectively is still unclear. Snelson (2011) states that a study on the perception of the usage of YouTube in ESL classroom for undergraduate students is a relatively new field of study and not much literature has been published regarding the subject especially in the Nigerian context. Despite the importance of using YouTube in engaging students in the classroom, little research has been conducted to investigate the perceptions of Nigeria undergraduate in using YouTube in ESL classroom.

Concept of YouTube

YouTube (<http://www.YouTube.com>) is a Web 2.0 site that is primarily based around video sharing, commenting, and viewing. On this website, users can post self-created videos, create appropriate tags related to the video's content (taxonomy), write a title and description for the video's content, comment on his or her own or other users' videos, create or join other users' video channels on various topics of interest, search for videos based on titles or keywords, create video responses to others' videos, etc. According to Terantino (2011), YouTube is considered to be a Web 2.0 site and not merely a collection of information because members of the website share their work and participate in peer feedback through asynchronous interaction with other users.

YouTube and other ICT Tools in English as Second Language in Nigeria

Research into the use of YouTube in the classroom is a relatively new area of study. However, the use of YouTube and other ICT tools in language learning has become a popular discussion all over the world. Several scholars from different countries suggested that using ICT in the classroom is becoming more prevalent in coming years (Klimova & Poulouva; 2014, Nguyen & Tri, 2014). In Nigeria, the trend of using ICT, especially YouTube, enables students to learn actively and interactively in classrooms and is acknowledged and considered as one of the most significant changes in ESL classroom (Akintunde & Angulu, 2015). The youth today use technology like the internet more than any other methods as a medium of communication and socialization (Maisamari & Akintunde, 2019). Therefore, due to this reality, educators bring in YouTube into the classroom to suit with the students' preferences and interest thus will make learning more interesting (Nguyen & Tri, 2014).

Criteria for Using YouTube as an Educational Tool in Nigeria

Among the key factors for YouTube's success are the following:

Accessibility: one can use it everywhere, anytime, and free of charge. It is user-friendly allowing an easy upload of videos that one can subscribe to on different channels. YouTube is authentic and offers rich multicultural content that provides a unique insight into the target culture. The easy connection with other social media enables cooperation, for instance sharing videos and communicating when rating and commenting on videos. It is available on multiple devices including mobile which make it a perfect medium for education. Media agreement, meaning the use of media our students interact with on a daily basis. It is an important factor when choosing educational resources (Roodt & Peier, 2013). On the downside, nowadays, YouTube is very ad-based and there is a lot of inappropriate content. The availability of videos might change and some videos that are copyright protected are unrightfully uploaded on YouTube.

YouTube, Students' Motivation and Learning among Nigerian Students

The use of YouTube has given positive impacts to the students' motivation. As stated by Brunner (2013), videos can have a strong effect on their minds and senses. He also suggested that the use of video clips need to be inserted in multimedia

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presentation to improve learning in higher educational institutions. These included using videos to grab students' attention, improve students' concentration, generate interests in the lesson, improve attitudes towards content, draw on students' imagination and make learning fun and meaningful. Chhabra (2012) also claimed that YouTube videos are not only able to attract the students' attention, but can cater for different learning styles namely: verbal, visual, musical, and emotional intelligences. Watching videos also allows the brain to react actively to both side of the brain which helps to increase and enhance students' understanding (Chhabra, 2012). Students' motivation to learn is much relies on their learning styles. According to Romanelli, Bird and Ryan (2009) have proposed that the definition of 'learning styles' is characterise by cognitive, effective and psychosocial behaviors that serve as relatively stable indicators of how learners perceive, interact with and respond to the learning environment. Many scholars have introduced different models of learning styles. Walter Burke Barbe which proposed three learning modalities known as VAK a) visual, b) auditory and kinesthetic learning and this model is a mixture of preferences, strengths and personality which is a mixture in each individual. This model was later refined by Fleming and Mills (1992) by introducing Neil Fleming's VARK model. Neil Fleming's VARK model which has been expanded upon earlier notions of sensory modalities such as the VAK model of Barbe and colleagues and the representational systems (VAKOG) in neurolinguistic programming. The four sensory modals in Fleming's model are; 1) Visual learning, 2) Auditory learning, 3) Read/write learning and 4) Kinesthetic learning.

Fleming and Mills (1992) claimed that visual learners have a preference of seeing visual aids that represented ideas using methods other than words, such as graphs, chart, diagrams, symbols and others. Auditory learners learn better through lectures, discussions and using tapes whereas tactile or kinesthetic learners prefer to learn via experience such as moving, touching example through science projects and experiments. The selection of YouTube among students is very much influenced by their learning styles preferences and interest. Klimova and Poulouva (2014) suggested several specific examples on how YouTube could be integrated and embedded into teaching and learning in ESL classroom. Some of the activities suggested are asking the students to create a video as a part of an assessment, record a video of a guest presenter and upload it on YouTube and use the comments functionality as a platform for discussion. Besides that, they also suggested that the students can search for videos that are related to questions posted at the end of lectures and educators can show students the real-world examples of material and theory covered in class as well as ask students to post video vignettes (Klimova & Poulouva, 2014). Another research was conducted by Roodt and De Villiers (2011) which was a study on using YouTube as a tool to support collaborative learning. The study was conducted on a first year of IS course at the University of Pretoria. The course included a group project in which students used YouTube to create a video on how businesses can use Web 2.0 technologies amongst other tasks. It was reported that from a sample of 185 students, it was found that YouTube was perceived as an innovative learning technology by the majority of the students (Roodt & De Villiers, 2011). Tan and Pearce (2012) agreed that the use of YouTube videos helped students to explain key ideas in a sociology course. They used these videos in an introductory sociology course at the Foundation Centre at Durham University. Tan and Pearce (2012) used these videos to illustrate important topics by giving explanation and discussion in the class and in smaller group environments. Tan and Pearce (2012) further explained that the use of YouTube videos helped students and was seen as an effective way to support their learning.

Types of Videos in YouTube

There are two types of videos that one will use when trying to learn a foreign language through YouTube. The first kind of video is the kind created by language teachers who explain a certain grammar point or give some type of lesson in the language. This is probably the best kind of video if one is just beginning. Often, one can get access to a variety of videos where people whose profession is to teach the language will sit down and teach someone a grammar point or two. This is an excellent way to learn and one can find these videos by searching on YouTube for "learn Spanish" for instance, if one is interested in learning Spanish (Roodt & Peier, 2013). The second kind of video is the kind that is created by native speakers of the language one is trying to learn. One can find video blogs and other types of entertainment videos. This is probably best if one is an intermediate or advanced level. Usually, these types of videos are fun to watch, so, it shouldn't feel too much like "studying" or "doing work". What one should do is watch these videos and use them to discover new words that one doesn't know or sentence structures and grammar that someone isn't aware of before (Duffy, 2018).

Language Learning Resources on YouTube

The abundance of online materials and resources on YouTube is overwhelming. Among the producers of these materials are media corporations, universities, schools, or major language product providers as well as individuals. They create everything from very professional over semi-professional to rather silly products that can be really attractive and helpful for

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students or just a waste of time. A thorough research for interesting and demanding language related videos is time consuming but definitely a good investment for future lesson preparation. In 2012, YouTube has launched different channels for educational purposes to facilitate the implementation of videos in education creating a safer environment for students without inappropriate contents or distracting videos <http://www.YouTube.com/education>

Limitations of YouTube

Educationalists mentioned two points about using YouTube in education. The first one is that YouTube addresses visual and auditory learners as they can watch and listen. As Zimmerman (2010) states, "I can imagine using a YouTube video and students following directions for movement, incorporating the bodily/kinesthetic intelligence, and so" (p. 189). In searching the YouTube website, one can find different teachers using YouTube for kinesthetic intelligence. For example, Professor Acton, a researcher spends years incorporating the bodily intelligence to improve students' pronunciation, uses YouTube to help students to improve their pronunciation in their preparation for TOEFL (for instance, *TOEFL iBTSpeaking Warm-up* at TOEFL® TV - The Official TOEFL Channel on YouTube. This video receives more positive reactions from language YouTube learners (Snelson, 2011). Another point is the control of the comments and the viewers of the YouTube. People think that YouTube has less privacy. However, many features of YouTube give instructors control over who will watch their videos and what comments appear under their videos too. Tracking the YouTube statistics shows that this website grows significantly in the cyberspace. In addition, the website shows concern about the problems that teachers have about using the YouTube in their classrooms (Snelson, 2011). For example, the instructors in the United States complain about the access of the website in their schools. Some US schools have blocked the YouTube website because students might use it for non-educational purposes. Therefore, YouTube has launched a new version of the portal called 'YouTube for Schools' to make the website available in every school in the United States (Roodt & Peier, 2013).

Benefits of YouTube to Nigerian Students

YouTube is a powerful personal branding tool that allows one to use one's images and links to one's site. The benefits according to Terantino (2011) are enumerated below:

1. People love to watch videos. Video gives your readers/customers an opportunity to see what you have to offer. Approximately 65% of the population learns or responds to visual methods of information.
2. It's an effective form of free advertising. Your YouTube page is an opportunity for you to advertise to the entire world without spending a dime.
3. It's global. YouTube is available in 22 countries.
4. YouTube can help your website go viral. Viewers have the choice to share your video on Face book, Twitter, Stumble Upon, Digg, and more.
5. It allows for others to share your videos and embed your video on their site.
6. It increases your chances of showing up in search engine search results because Google owns YouTube and they work together.
7. Your video may be displayed as a suggestion in other videos that are related to yours.
8. Is rated the 3rd most visited website according to Alexia.
9. It exceeds 2 billion views a day.
10. The average person spends approximately 15 minutes a day on YouTube.
11. Over 3 million people are connected and are sharing the videos to at least one major social networking site (Duffy, 2018).
12. You can comment on videos through your YouTube channel, which will increase the traffic to your channel. Subscribe and comment on videos that are related to your niche.
13. People can subscribe to you and they will be notified every time you upload a video.

The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools. Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. The ELT classes have been using the videos for teaching English language skills since many years now. The organizations like BBC and CNN have even made billions of dollars selling the video content for teaching purposes. Money and Time - are two things which have been creating so many hurdles in accessing the authentic video content in the past time (Stoks, 2013). But for last three and a half years, YouTube, a video content sharing website has been making the difference to

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it. At YouTube, anyone can post / access video content. YouTube now contains enormous amount of video content, some of which is highly exploitable in the classroom.

The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools (Akintunde & Akuta, 2022). Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. Some of them are: (a). Autos & Vehicles (b). Comedy (c). Education (d). Entertainment (e). Film and Animation (f). Gaming (g). How to and Style (h). Music (i). News and Politics (j). Nonprofits and Activism (k). People and Blogs (l). Pets and Animals (m). Science and Technology (n). Sports (o). Travel and Events.

The real advantage of YouTube - at least from a language learning point of view - is that, it offers authentic examples of everyday English used by everyday people. Yes, this is the challenge as well. Students may enjoy watching these clips, but poor sound quality, pronunciation and slang can make these short videos even more difficult to understand. At the same time use of YouTube videos enables teachers to attach the students to the "real life" nature of these videos. By creating context for these short videos' students can be helped to explore a world of online English learning possibilities. YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom for various teaching vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not (Stoks, 2013).

YouTube and Video Sharing

Over the past year, YouTube has become enormously popular. What is common to most clips is that they are amateur videos which document occurrences from the lives of non-celebrities. As such, the clips provide a huge multimedia library of real language use by real people, a potentially rich resource for language learning or corpus collections (Tan & Pearce, 2012). The vast majority of clips are in English, and a number of ESL/EFL teachers have begun tapping into this source. While some provide sample lessons for students to view and discuss, others have uploaded videos of their own, with the specific goal of language learning in mind. Instructors of other languages, including Spanish, French, Japanese and Indonesian, have also found YouTube to be useful in language learning. One of the differences between YouTube and other social networking sites is that it does not feature community tagging (Roodt & Peier, 2013). Rather, the user posting the video supplies the tags. As is the case in most social networking sites, there are no prescribed, or even recommended, content tags. This makes searching for particular kinds of video clips or specific content very much a hit or miss enterprise (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011). Searching on "Teaching English," for example, returns hundreds of results, most of them clips of teachers in action or class profiles, but the hit list also includes commercials that could be used in teaching English, as well as clips from commercial providers of language instruction (Tan & Pearce, 2012). As with all clips on YouTube, clips in this category vary greatly in video professionalism, length, audio quality, and interest level for folks other than those directly involved as camera operators or subjects (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011).

Quite a few group projects from language classes are posted to YouTube as a method of sharing and publicizing. Some of the clips uploaded are just slideshows or videos shot with a static camera; others, however, are quite sophisticated in the use of lighting, captioning, camera angles, and transitions. Many come with a music soundtrack, often using commercially available songs, which for the time being some copyright holders (i.e. record companies) are allowing to be used in this way. The murky permission issues in the incorporation of copyrighted audio and video in uploaded clips to YouTube result in some clips being suddenly pulled from the site (Tan & Pearce, 2012). This makes problematic any reliance on the availability of particular clips for instructional purposes. Uploading video clips to YouTube is a quick and easy process and works in similar ways on other video sharing sites. Video clips can be in AVI, move, or mpg formats (MPEG4) and be a maximum of ten minutes long. At least one content tag is required, along with a specification of the language used in the clip, presently restricted to a choice among English, Spanish, French, Japanese, Chinese, or German. Clips can also be uploaded directly from a digital camera or a PDA, as long as they are connected to the Internet (Roodt & De-Villiers, 2011). Video can even be directly uploaded to YouTube from a Webcam. Once uploaded, the file is converted to the Flash video format used for all clips. The URL is displayed to the uploader, along with the HTML code to paste into a Web page in order to display the video on one's own page. The ease with which anyone is able to upload video clips to sites such as YouTube, along with the popularity of shooting videos on cell phones or digital cameras has enabled the video sharing frenzy the Nigeria is currently experiencing. What also has contributed to this development is the rapid growth in broadband Internet connections in Nigeria, as well as the increase in processor speeds in computers, making video editing and format conversion/compression significantly faster. This has been accompanied by the availability of inexpensive yet powerful video editing tools such as movie for the Macintosh or Jump cut, Videoegg, or Eyespot for Windows (Tan & Pearce, 2012). These products have specific tools for creating videos to be delivered in a Web browser. One of the most significant enabling technologies for the new video Internet age is the Flash

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video format, which is quickly becoming the format of choice for video on the Web, used by YouTube as well as by Google Video, MySpace, and many other sites.

Conclusion

The use of technology has become increasingly important in language teaching and learning. The successful use of technology, however, requires that language teachers have the necessary technical competence and pedagogical knowledge. The English Language Teaching process has been energized with the emergence of new Internet technologies and now the Web tools. Also, using videos for language teaching has been one of the most effective ways to achieve success in the classroom. The ELT classes have been using the videos for teaching English language skills since many years now. The real advantage of YouTube - at least from a language learning point of view - is that it offers authentic examples of everyday English used by everyday people. Nevertheless, acquiring 21st century skills through meaningful project-based teaching and learning scenarios requires effort and time. Consultations and the support of the student during the language learning process become more and more important. With the evolution of the Web, YouTube will provide a broader spectrum of functionality, for instance, using exact word and phrase search that will prove to be especially useful for language learning. The automatic creation of subtitles that is already available for some videos will improve over time and provide additional opportunities for meaningful language learning. The integration of assessment tools and tools for cooperation will improve the use of YouTube as an educational tool. The YouTube channels dedicated to education will hopefully grow in future and offer a protected environment for learning and community specific knowledge bases. As educators consider the use of YouTube video as important, thus, they must strongly consider what students' think and feel about these tools in their courses. Therefore, using YouTube videos as one and readily available source of authentic material will encourage the students to interact actively in class and further develop their language skills as they are eager to gain deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Recommendations

1. The use of YouTube videos enables teachers to attach the students to the "real life" nature of these videos. By creating context for these short videos, teachers can help students to explore a world of online English learning possibilities.
2. YouTube videos can be used in an ELT classroom by teachers for various teaching such as vocabulary, accents, pronunciations, voice modulation and what not.
3. YouTube has the potential to be a useful educational tool that offers endless opportunities for formal and informal student centered language learning approaches. For teachers to engage students in meaningful learning scenarios, learners must be enabled to connect previous knowledge to new information as well as incorporate higher and lower order thinking skills.

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